

Benzidine Rearrangement in Heterocyclic Series. Part III.

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In a recent communication, Bose and Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 643) showed that 1-*o*-tolyl- and 1-*m*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazides condense readily with halogenated ketones forming hydrazo-compounds which undergo benzidine rearrangement (*cf.* Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 331). 1-*p*-Tolylthiosemicarbazide, however, was found to behave in a different manner and formed imino-compounds. In the present investigation the action of the three nitrophenylthiosemicarbazides upon halogenated ketones has been studied.

The reaction proceeded smoothly at the room temperature with the formation of products which could be divided into two classes:

(1) Those that behaved like hydrazobenzene towards hydrochloric acid, *e g.*, the products derived from 1-*m*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide.

(2) Those that were unaffected by boiling hydrochloric acid but dissolved in aqueous ammonia or caustic alkalis with a deep violet colour. This group includes the products from the other two nitrophenylthiosemicarbazides.

In all the cases, the substances gave colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and yielded monoacetyl derivatives on acetylation with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine.

The course of the reaction may be represented as follows in the case of (1).

The case of α -naphthylhydrazinethiazoles, which were studied in this connexion, is also interesting from the point of view of the above statement. The compounds, which were prepared by condensing equimolecular quantities of 1- α -naphthylthiosemicarbazide and halogenated ketones at the ordinary temperature, shared all the properties of phenylhydrazinethiazoles described by Bose (*loc.cit.*) Obviously, the naphthalene-thiazole system comes under the generalisation proposed above.

Further investigations with symmetrically disubstituted hydrazines having pyridine, *iso*quinoline and other heterocyclic ring systems are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-o-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide.—*o*-Nitrophenylhydrazine (15 g.) and potassium sulphocyanide (15 g.) were successively added to 60 c.c. of absolute alcohol containing dry hydrogen chloride gas (3.5 g.). The mixture was boiled on a water-bath under reflux for eight hours. The contents of the flask were then diluted with water (150 c.c.) and a little hydrochloric acid, and cooled when 1-*o*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide separated out (9 g.). It was crystallised from acetone in yellow plates, m.p. 201°. (Found: N, 26.12. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires N, 26.42 per cent.).

The method of preparation of the other thiosemicarbazides (*vide infra*) is essentially the same as described above.

1-*o*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromoacetophenone:
Formation of VII (R=Ph).

1-*o*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (20 c.c.) and ω -bromoacetophenone (1.9 g.) was added gradually to the cold solution with constant shaking. The reaction was followed by development of heat and appearance of the condensation product. After a few minutes pyridine (4 c. c.) was added when the product dissolved. Water was then added to precipitate the base which was then collected and washed with water and dilute alcohol (yield almost quantitative). The substance was crystallised from acetone (charcoaled) in brown plates which decomposed at 190°. (Found: C, 57.63; H, 3.77; N, 18.12. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S$ requires C, 57.69; H, 3.85; N, 17.95 per cent.).

The substance is soluble in alcohol, acetone and pyridine. It gives a deep brown colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. It dissolves in caustic alkalis giving a deep violet solution. It remained unchanged even on prolonged boiling with hydrochloric acid.

The *monoacetyl* derivative, obtained in the usual manner, crystallised from acetone (charcoaled) in yellow needles, m. p. 175°. (Found: N, 15.96. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 15.82 per cent.).

1-*o*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and *p*-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone: *Formation of VII* [R = $CH_3.C_6H_4$ - (para)].

The procedure was similar to that described above (yield, 1.6 g. from 1.6 g. of 1-*o*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide). The product formed orange needles from acetone, m. p. 185° with decomp. (Found: N, 17.12. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17.18 per cent.). In properties and solubilities it resembled the phenyl compound described above.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone in yellow plates, m. p. 206°. (Found: N, 15.16. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 15.22 per cent.).

1-*o*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and Monochloroacetone: *Formation of VII* (R = CH_3).

The product, when prepared and purified as stated above, formed yellow plates (from acetone) which assumed a dark colour on standing. It decomposed at 165°. (Found: N, 22.16. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22.4 per cent.).

The substance gave a greenish-brown colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and a deep violet solution with caustic alkalis or ammonia.

The *monoacetyl* derivative separated from acetone in yellow needles, m. p. 167°. (Found: C, 48.9; H, 4.42; N, 19.39.

$C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_4S$ requires C, 49.32; H, 4.11; N, 19.18 per cent.).

1-m-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide.—From 17 g. of *m*-nitrophenylhydrazine, 10 g. of the product were obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol in orange-yellow aggregates, m. p. 187°. (Found: N, 26.62. $C_7H_8O_2N_4S$ requires N, 26.42 per cent.).

2-m-Nitrophenylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, R=Ph).—*1-m*-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (1.8 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol and ω -bromoacetophenone (1.7 g.) added at the ordinary temperature (25°). Subsequent procedure was as usual, the yield being 2.4 g. The base was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol in yellow, star-like crystals melting at 192–3°. (Found: N, 18.17. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17.95 per cent.).

It was soluble in acetone, alcohol, and pyridine and gave a deep reddish-brown colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. Caustic alkalis have no action upon it in the cold.

The *monoacetyl* derivative was crystallised from acetone in straw-yellow needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: N, 15.79. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 15.82 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-o-nitro-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, R=Ph).—The hydrazinethiazole described above (1.5 g.) was boiled with 130 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (1:3) for 45 minutes until it had completely dissolved. The solution was then filtered and cooled. On neutralising the solution with concentrated ammonia, a precipitate (0.9 g.) was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol (charcoaled) in reddish-orange needles, m.p. 253°. (Found: N, 17.97. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17.95 per cent.).

The base did not impart to sulphuric acid any colour. It formed a *picrate*, m.p. 213° (brown plates).

The *dihydrochloride* was obtained by dissolving the base in hot dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was treated with animal charcoal and filtered hot. On adding concentrated hydrochloric acid and allowing to stand, the hydrochloride crystallised out in light yellow needles which decomposed at 230°. (Found: Cl, 18.02. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 18.42 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone in orange plates, decomposing above 295°. (Found: N, 14.13. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 14.14 per cent.).

2-m-Nitrophenylhydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, R=p-Tolyl).—The condensation was carried out in acetone solution

using equimolecular quantities of 1-*m*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone. The product crystallised from acetone in buff-coloured needles, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 59.22; H, 4.67; N, 17.19. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires C, 58.9; H, 4.29; N, 17.18 per cent.). It gave a deep brown colouration with sulphuric acid.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 15.26. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 15.20 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-p-tolyl-5-o-nitro-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, R=*p*-Tolyl).—The hydrochloride of the base was found to be sparingly soluble even in boiling water. Hence the conversion was effected in alcoholic medium, the duration of heating under reflux being about two hours. The product crystallised from alcohol in deep brown plates, m. p. 163° with decomp. (Found: N, 17.37. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17.18 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative formed brownish needles (from alcohol) melting at 253° with decomposition. (Found: N, 13.65. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 13.75 per cent.).

2-m-Nitrophenylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula I, R=CH₃).—Equimolecular quantities of monochloroacetone and 1-*m*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide were employed, as in the previous cases, the medium being alcohol. The base crystallised from acetone in dark plates decomposing at 138°. (Found: N, 22.38. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22.40 per cent.).

The base gave a greenish-brown colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone in orange crystals, m. p. 155°. (Found: N, 19.45. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 19.18 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-o-nitro-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula II, R=CH₃).—The thiazole described above (Formula I, R=CH₃) was boiled with 2*N*-hydrochloric acid. It readily dissolved forming an orange-red solution which turned yellow on further boiling. The filtered solution was cooled and treated with an excess of ammonia. The base was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol in deep brown needles, which decomposed at 110°. (Found: S, 12.93. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires S, 12.80 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative formed yellow crystals (from methyl alcohol) decomposing at 180°. (Found: N, 17.12. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_4S$ requires N, 16.77 per cent.).

1-p-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide.—Of the three nitrophenylthiosemicarbazides, the yield, under identical conditions, was found to be greatest in the case of the *para*-compound, 15 g. of *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine giving 18 g. of the product. It was first crystallised from pyridine and finally from alcohol in yellow aggregates melting at 203°. (Found: S, 14.85. $C_7H_8O_2N_4S$ requires S, 15.09 per cent.).

1-p-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromoacetophenone: Formation of V (R=Ph).—The usual method was followed. The product separated from acetone in shining, brown plates, m. p. 189° with decomp. (Found: C, 57.63; H, 3.91; N, 17.91. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_4S$ requires C, 57.69; H, 3.85; N, 17.95 per cent.).

It gave a deep brown colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and a deep violet colour with caustic soda solution.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in shining, white plates, m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 15.87. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 15.82 per cent.).

1-p-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and p-Methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone: Formation of V (R=p-Tolyl).—The resulting product formed light brown plates from acetone, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 17.22. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 17.18 per cent.).

This compound, like the phenyl derivative, imparted a deep brown colour to concentrated sulphuric acid and an intense violet colour to caustic alkalis.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone in white needles, m.p. 182°. (Found: N, 15.26. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 15.20 per cent.).

1-p-Nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide and Monochloroacetone: (Formation of V (R=CH₃)).—The resulting product formed yellow aggregates, when crystallised from acetone. It decomposed at 145°. (Found: N, 22.17. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires N, 22.4 per cent.).

The substance imparted a greenish-yellow colour to concentrated sulphuric acid and a violet colour to aqueous alkali solutions.

The *monoacetyl* derivative crystallised from acetone in white needles, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 19.09. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_4S$ requires N, 19.18 per cent.).

2- α -Naphthylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula VIII, R=Ph).—Obtained in the usual way from 1- α -naphthylthiosemicarbazide and ω -bromoacetophenone, the base was found to be hardly

soluble in alcohol and acetone. It was crystallised from hot pyridine by the addition of alcohol in almost colourless plates, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 13.85. $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$ requires N, 13.25 per cent.).

It imparted a corn-flower blue colour to concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *monoacetyl* derivative separated from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 160–161°. (Found: N, 11.8. $C_{21}H_{17}ON_3S$ requires N, 11.7 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-(4'-amino)-naphthyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IX, R=Ph).—The naphthyl compound described above (2 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) and rectified spirit (60 c.c.) were boiled together for half an hour. The base was isolated by making the solution alkaline with ammonia (yield, 1.8 g.). It was finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 236° with decomposition. (Found: C, 71.83; H, 4.79. $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$ requires C, 71.93; H, 4.73 per cent.).

The substance gave no colouration with sulphuric acid.

It formed a *picrate*, crystallisable from alcohol in yellow plates, m.p. 193°.

The *dihydrochloride* was obtained by dissolving the base in alcohol and passing hydrochloric acid gas. It formed white needles, m.p. 245° with decomp. (Found: Cl, 17.95. $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 18.30 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative was very soluble in ethyl alcohol, acetone, acetic acid, benzene and ether. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless aggregates, m.p. 248°. (Found: N, 10.62. $C_{23}H_{19}N_3SO_2$ requires N, 10.50 per cent.).

2- α -Naphthylhydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula VIII, R=p-Tolyl).—The product was scarcely soluble in alcohol and acetone. When crystallised from hot pyridine by the addition of alcohol, it formed brownish needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: C, 72.42; H, 5.30. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3S$ requires C, 72.51; H, 5.15 per cent.).

It gave a deep blue colour with concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *monoacetyl* derivative was crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 161°. (Found: N, 11.27. $C_{22}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires N, 11.26 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-p-tolyl-5-(4'-amino)-naphthyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IX, R=p-Tolyl).—The resulting base, after the usual treatment with alkali, was crystallised in colourless needles from acetone, m.p.

280°. It gave no colouration with sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 12.39. $C_{20}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 12.38 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative was crystallised from methyl alcohol; m. p. 208°. (Found: N, 9.95. $C_{24}N_{21}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 10.12 per cent.).

2- α -Naphthylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IX, R = CH_3).—Slow crystallisation of the product (from monochloroacetone and 1- α -naphthylthiosemicarbazide) from pyridine and dilute alcohol gave long fibrous needles, m. p. 188° with decomp. (Found: N, 16.03. $C_{14}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.).

It imparted a greenish-blue colour to concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *monoacetyl* compound was crystallised from methyl alcohol; m. p. 149-150°. (Found: N, 14.21. $C_{16}H_{15}ON_3S$ requires N, 14.14 per cent.).

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-(4'-amino-)-naphthyl-1:3-thiazole (Formula IX, R = CH_3).—The base was boiled for half an hour with hydrochloric acid (1:1). On adding ammonia to the filtered and cooled solution, a tarry mass was obtained which solidified on standing.

It was found to be extremely soluble in ethyl alcohol, acetone and methyl alcohol. From benzene it separated in brown crystals which decomposed at 110°. (Found: N, 16.42. $C_{14}H_{13}N_3S$ requires N, 16.28 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative was crystallised from methyl alcohol. It decomposed at 260°. (Found: N, 12.31. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 12.39 per cent.).

In conclusion, we offer our best thanks to Sir P. C. Rây for his keen interest during this investigation.